

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECIAL DATA (cm⁻¹)

CH ₃ CONHCH ₃ , (liquid)	Zn(CH ₃ CONHCH ₃) ₂ Cl ₂	Zn(CH ₃ CONHCH ₃) ₂ Br ₂	Zn(CH ₃ CONHCH ₃) ₂ I ₂	Assignment
3300s	3890	3886	3876	N-H stretching vibration (bonded)
3110s	2940s	2940w	2946m	C-H stretching vibration (sym)
2940s				
2890sh	2715w	2712w	2710w	
2720w				
1653s	1660	1666s	1666s	Amide I
1567s	1530s	1524s	1505s	Amide II
1445m	1450m	1450m	1462s	CH ₃ N deformation vibration
1413s	1422m	1426m	1430m	(sym)
1373s	1380s	1385s	1386s	CH ₃ C deformation (sym)
1299s	1310s	1322s	1318s	Amide III
1159s	1162m	1160m	1160m	CH ₃ N rocking vibration
1096m	1095w	1096m	1098m	CH ₃ -N, CH ₃ -C stretching vibration
1040m	1040m	1045m	1046m	CH ₃ C rocking
937m	950w		945m	
881m	885w	890w	892w	N-H-out of plane bending vibration CH ₃ -C rocking
725m				
	236m	248m	240m	M-N mode
	326s	305s	300s	
	298m	270m	280m	M-X vibration

s=Strong, m=medium, w=weak, sh=shoulder,
sym=symmetric, Amide I=(C=O) stretching vibration
Amide II=N-H deformation vibration or C-H stretching vibration,
Amide III=O-C-N and N-H vibrations, X-Cl, Br, I.

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Determination of Gold and Copper with *p*-(2-Mercaptopropionamido)benzoic Acid as a Gravimetric Reagent

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GOLD is normally determined by reduction to the metallic state¹. Complex-forming organic precipitants are very few indeed. *p*-(2-Mercaptopropionamido)benzoic acid², which was introduced as a valuable reagent for the determination of silver and mercury, has been observed to complex Au(I) which is precipitated quantitatively at pH 0.5 to 3.5. Cu(II), too, is precipitated quantitatively at pH 2.0 to 4.8, however, gold can be separated from Cu(II) by sequestering the latter with EDTA. Au(III) is reduced to Au(I) before complexation. The reagent offers the advantages of adequate solubility in aqueous medium, ease of preparation and selectivity of reaction.

Determination of Au(I) and Cu(II) :

Twenty ml of the solution (0.2%, m/V, of gold solution and 0.1%, m/V, of copper solution were used) of the cation to be estimated is taken in a

beaker and diluted to about 125 ml. Required amount of 3N HCl is introduced to adjust the pH at 0.5 to 1.5 and 2.0 to 3.0 for gold and copper respectively. The solution is heated on a water bath and the reagent solution (0.5%, m/V, in 10% ethanol) is introduced dropwise with constant stirring. The precipitate, thus obtained, is digested for an hour, filtered through a sintered glass crucible G4, washed with hot water to remove any adhering reagent and dried to a constant weight at 120°. The weights of the complexes multiplied by 0.46790 and 0.22078 give the weights of gold and copper respectively.

Determinations in the presence of Diverse ions :

The reagent is quite selective for the determination of Au(I) and Cu(II). The presence of alkali metals, alkaline earths, ammonium, Zn(II), Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Fe(III), Cd(II), Pb(II), Bi(III), Tl(I), Th(IV), Zr(IV), Ce(IV) and other rare earths, VO(II), UO₂(II) and molybdate does not impair the determinations of Au(I) and Cu(II). Tungstate does not interfere with the determinations, however, the determinations were carried out at pH 3.0 in order to prevent the precipitation of tungstic acid. Au(I) is determined in the presence of Cu(II) by masking the latter with EDTA at pH 3.0.

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Synthesis of Dithiotetrathiazoline Diones

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THIAZOLINES and their derivatives have drawn the attention of scientists due to their prodigious range of activity¹. They are chiefly used as analgesics, nematocides, bactericides, fungicides, vulcanisation accelerators, etc. These compounds are also popular for their radio protective activities in the present day therapy.

A perusal of literature reveals that no work has been done on the reaction of chloranil with substituted dithiocarbamates.

In continuation to our work on pyrrocoline quinones^{2,3}, thiadiazolobenzimidazoles⁴, the present communication describes the synthesis of a series of new thiazoline diones by condensing chloranil with substituted ammonium dithiocarbamates. The products isolated were 3 : 7-disubstituted 2 : 6-dithio 1 : 3 : 5 : 7 tetrathiazoline 4 : 8 diones(I).

TABLE 1—3 : 7-DISUBSTITUTED 2 : 6-DITHIO 1 : 3 : 5 : 7-TETRATHIAZOLINE 4 : 8-DIONES

Sl. No.	R	Molecular formula	Yield %	M.P. °C	% Analysis		I. R. data
					Calcd.	Found	
1.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ S ₄ N ₂ O ₂	57	>350	C, 54.8 H, 2.2 N, 6.4	54.2 1.8 6.2	C=S 1185 cm ⁻¹ , C=C 1610 cm ⁻¹ , C=O 1660 cm ⁻¹
2.	p-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₈ S ₄ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂	50	>350	C, 35.0 H, 1.9 N, 6.8	34.4 1.6 6.4	C=S 1210 cm ⁻¹ , C=C 1605 cm ⁻¹ , C=O 1665 cm ⁻¹
3.	o-OH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ S ₄ N ₂ O ₂	45	327	C, 56.6 H, 3.0 N, 6.0	56.1 2.7 5.6	C=S 1190 cm ⁻¹ , C=C 1600 cm ⁻¹ , C=O 1675 cm ⁻¹
4.	m-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ S ₄ N ₂ O ₂	37	314	C, 56.6 H, 3.0 N, 6.0	56.3 2.4 5.7	C=S 1180 cm ⁻¹ , C=C 1625 cm ⁻¹ , C=O 1685 cm ⁻¹
5.	p-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ S ₄ N ₂ O ₂	41	270 (decomp.)	C, 56.6 H, 3.0 N, 6.0	56.0 2.7 5.5	C=S 1195 cm ⁻¹ , C=C 1620 cm ⁻¹ , C=O 1675 cm ⁻¹
6.	o-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₈ S ₄ N ₂ O ₆	32	305	C, 45.4 H, 1.5 N, 5.3	45.2 1.2 5.0	C=S 1190 cm ⁻¹ , C=C 1605 cm ⁻¹ , C=O 1665 cm ⁻¹
7.	m-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₈ S ₄ N ₂ O ₆	41	>350	C, 45.4 H, 1.5 N, 5.3	45.0 1.1 5.1	C=S 1230 cm ⁻¹ , C=C 1610 cm ⁻¹ , C=O 1680 cm ⁻¹
8.	p-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₈ S ₄ N ₂ O ₆	37	319	C, 45.4 H, 1.5 N, 5.3	45.3 1.8 4.8	C=S 1215 cm ⁻¹ , C=C 1600 cm ⁻¹ , C=O 1670 cm ⁻¹